

DYNAMIC PERFORMANCE OF MARINE SANDWICH PANEL STRUCTURES

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1 Introduction

Sandwich panels are widely used within the marine industry, particularly as primary hull shell structure, but also as appendages and deck housings. Hydrodynamic loads can be very significant for these structures, particularly for high speed craft. The usual design approach for hull panels treats them as being subjected to a uniformly distributed static pressure whose magnitude is given by empirical formulae. This approach is embedded within many scantling codes and is also used for analytical and numerical analyses of panels. In reality the water pressure acting on most hull structures is neither uniformly distributed nor static. In particular, slamming events typically generate high magnitude pressure pulses of very short duration that move across the panel as the hull enters the water as shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Traditional quasi-static panel design methods have long been used for materials dominated by bending stresses and deformation, such as metals and single skin composite construction. However these design methodologies underestimate the maximum transverse shear force on sandwich panels [1, 2]. Core shear is a common failure mode experienced by vessels with sandwich hull construction when subjected to slamming loads.

This paper describes an experimental study of sandwich composite panels subjected to transverse water impact loads in a controlled velocity laboratory test facility. Transient responses and the resulting failure of the panel are characterized. The focus of the paper is to determine the differences in panel responses during a slamming event to those predicted by traditional analysis approaches based on uniform pressure loads.

2 Methodology

Water impact testing of sandwich panels was carried out on a Servo-hydraulic Slam testing System (SSTS). The testing rig with a specimen in place is shown in Figure 3. This system has been used previously for a significant amount of research on the topic of hull slamming. A more detailed description of the SSTS and previous testing is given in references [2,3,4].

The SSTS uses a cylindrical water tank with a diameter of 3.5 m and a water depth of typically 1.4 m. A steel frame supports the hydraulic ram, manifold, servo-valve, accumulators and associated plumbing above the tank. The specimen fixture, which is attached to the hydraulic ram, slides on vertical rails and hence moves in one degree of freedom. The deadrise angle of the panel can be changed from 0° to 40° in 10° increments. Panel specimens typically have dimensions of approximately 1000x500 mm. Two hydraulic accumulators supply oil to the ram and the velocity is controlled by a servo-valve and a closed-loop PID controller using position and acceleration feedback. Three vertical panels, two on the sides and one behind the panel constrain the flow along the panel. The servo-hydraulic ram has a stroke of 1.4m, typically including approximately 0.4m travelled in air prior to impact, then up to 0.5 m travelled during the impact event, and a further 0.5 m if required for the specimen to stop. The SSTS can achieve velocities of up to approximately 10 m/s. The hydraulic system hardware and software is custom designed and manufactured for this application, with many unique features to achieve the required combination of high velocity and force, and accurate control of motion during the slamming event. During the impacts the applied load and corresponding panel responses are recorded using a

variety of load cells, strain gauges, displacement transducers and pressure transducers along with a high speed data acquisition system.

For this test series the specimens had external dimensions of 565 mm by 1030 mm, with an unsupported region between simply supported edges of 500x1000 mm. The laminates consisted of PVC foam cores, and either glass fibre/epoxy (G-C70) or carbon fibre/epoxy (C-C70) skins, as defined in Table 1. The specimens were designed to have different flexural stiffness while having similar shear stiffnesses.

Table 1 Panel Specifications

Materials	G-C70	C-C70
Reinforcement	Glass Fibre	Carbon Fibre
Orientation	(0/±45/90) ₄	(0/90) ₅
Core Material	PVC, Airex C70.140	
Dimensions		
Skin Thickness	2.5 mm	
Core Thickness	15 mm	
Properties		
Flexural Rigidity	6,740 Nm	25,500 Nm
Shear Stiffness	960,000 N/m	960,000 N/m

3 Results

3.1 Typical panel responses

Figure 4 presents typical pressure, panel displacement and strain results for a test at 3 m/s and 10° deadrise angle. The position of the transducers is as defined in Figure 5, with pressures measured at P1, P3 and P5, panel displacement at the centre of the panel (adjacent to P3), and strains measured on the inner panel skin at the centre (Strain 3, adjacent to P3) and near to the edge of the panel (Strain 5, adjacent to P5).

Figure 4 shows that the panel does not begin to deform until after the pressure pulse reaches P1 and that the maximum deformation of the panel occurs at a similar time as the pressure pulse reaches P5. This is expected, as at this stage the entire panel is being loaded, with most of the panel subjected to a distributed residual pressure, combined with the high pressure at the flow front near to the edge of the panel. The maximum strain at the centre of the panel (Strain 3) occurs slightly earlier than the maximum deflection, while there are only very small strains

near to the edge of the panel (Strain 5) until quite late in the slamming event, but then this strain increases rapidly as the flow front nears the panel edge.

3.2 Typical pressures

Figure 6 compares the transient pressures at transducers P1, P3 and P5 (positions as in Figure 5) in a 3m/s flexible panel test (GF skins) to those of a rigid panel structure. The pressure magnitudes and profile at P1 are very similar for the rigid and deformable panels. This is expected as the deformable panel does not deflect significantly until later in the slamming event as shown in Figure 4.

The pressures at P3 (panel centre) are significantly different, particularly the residual pressure which is initially higher for the deformable panel, then reduces to a similar level as the rigid panel at the end of the slamming event. The difference in the residual pressure is greater at higher impact velocity. At P5 the peak pressure for the deformable panel is higher than that for the rigid panel while the residual is similar.

These differences are believed to be related to the transient kinematic behaviour of the deformable panel during the slamming event. Figure 4 shows that the centre of the deformable panel deforms up to a maximum of approximately 8mm when impacted at 3 m/s and 10°. This has the effect of reducing the velocity of the panel relative to the water to approximately 2.2 m/s, thereby reducing the peak pressure. As the panel reaches its maximum deflection its relative velocity increases back to the velocity of the testing fixture, then increases further as the panel rebounds towards, and then beyond its initial position. This is believed to be the cause of the increased residual pressure at the panel centre.

The deformation in the vicinity of P5 (close to the panel boundary) is also significant, reaching approximately 4.3 mm at 3 m/s impact velocity. This deformation is measured approximately 35 mm from the chine boundary support, demonstrating that there is appreciable rotation of the panel in this region, presumably due to transverse shear deformation of the panel. The deformation has the effect of reducing the local deadrise angle, thereby increasing the local pressure.

The strain at P5 is proportional to the transverse shear force [2]. Figure 4 shows that the strain increases rapidly as the pressure peak passes, due to the high residual pressure combining with the moving peak pressure. This is of particular concern for sandwich panels as this is the region most highly loaded in transverse shear, and the position where core shear failure normally occurs.

3.2 Effect of impact velocity on strains

The structural response of the panel can be characterised through the strains measured on the inner skin of the panel. Strains at the panel centre and near to the panel edge can be used to determine the bending moment at these positions. Those close to the chine edge of the panel can also be used to estimate the resulting transverse shear force in this region [2]. Figure 7 presents the effect of impact velocity on strains at the centre and chine edge of the G-C70 and C-C70 panels. A second order trendline has been fitted to each of the sets of strain data. There is good correlation between the data and the trendlines with R^2 values of 0.975, 0.969, 0.981 and 0.994. This demonstrates that the strains are proportional to V^2 as expected since the pressure is proportional to velocity squared.

The G-C70 panel has higher strains than the C-C70 at all velocities at both the centre and the chine. This difference is due to the stiffness of the two panels. As shown in Table 1 the flexural rigidity of C-C70 is approximately 4 times greater than that of the G-C70 panel.

3.2 Effect of impact velocity on moments at panel centre and edge

The strains from Figure 7 can be used to determine the moments at the corresponding positions by applying classical sandwich theory, as in Equation 1.

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{M_x z}{D} \quad [1]$$

These moments are compared to analytical predictions based on the expected mean pressure on the panel from Payne's formulation [5], combined with Kirchoff-Love plate theory series solution for simply supported panels from Zenkert [6].

Payne's formulation [5] is a calculation of the hydrodynamic force based on the conservation of momentum considering the mass of water displaced during the impact of a wedge into water. This force is then averaged across the panel to create an equivalent mean pressure.

Figure 8 compares the resulting moments at the centre and chine of the flexible panels to those expected on the basis of a uniform pressure load from Payne's solution. The results from the flexible panels are normalised by dividing by the uniform equivalent pressure moment at each impact velocity. Hence a value of 1.0 would mean that the moment is the same as expected for the uniform pressure case.

Figure 8 shows that the moment at the centre of the flexible panels is slightly higher than for a uniform pressure case, particularly for smaller slamming impacts. The moment at the centre for the flexible panels is between 1.0 and 1.4 times greater for the C-C70 panel and 1.1 and 2.2 for the G-C70 panel. There is little variation with respect to the impact velocity.

The moment at the chine of the flexible panels is much higher than for the uniform case, with a maximum of approximately 10 times for the G-C70 panel at an impact velocity of 1m/s. At high impact velocities the difference reduces, but is still 5 times that for the uniformly loaded case at 4.5 m/s. This is particularly important for sandwich panels because this is the position of maximum transverse shear force, and where core failure typically occurs. The chine moment for the C-C70 panel is in the range of 3.5 to 6 times that for the uniformly loaded case over the range of impact velocities tested.

The differences between the moments measured on each of the flexible panels are related to the difference in their flexural and shear rigidities. The more flexible the panel is, the greater the variation in pressure from a uniform load.

4 Conclusions

Composite panels subjected to water impact slamming experience different pressures and resulting distributions of moments than predicted for uniform pressure loads. The moment at the centre for lower slamming velocities is relatively similar to that expected from classical uniform pressure based slamming analyses, but the moment close to the panel chine edge is much higher than predicted, in the cases tested up to 10 times the uniform pressure prediction. This results in higher than expected transverse shear forces, which can lead failure at the panel chine edge for sandwich structures.

A clear variation in moment measured at the chine can be seen between the two flexible panels tested. At 4.5m/s the difference is 30%. At higher slamming velocities the moment at the centre of the panels diverges from the classical uniform pressure based slamming predictions, particularly for the more flexible panels.

This variation is due to the varying flexural rigidity of the panels, which results in a difference in the applied pressure due to the transient kinematic behaviour of the deformable panels. This creates a hydroelastic coupling between the structural deformation and the fluid motion results in variations in both the fluid pressure and structural responses.

This work has highlighted the importance of considering the applied load during slamming as non-uniform when designing for sandwich structures. The increased bending moment at the chine seen for both of the flexible panels tested indicates the load at the chine is substantially under predicted using a traditional uniform pressure approach.

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Fig. 1. Schematic of slamming event

Fig. 2. Experimental pressure data for 5m/s water slam of rigid panel at 10° deadrise. Transducers are evenly spaced from P1 nearest to keel to P5 close to chine

Fig. 3. Panel specimen in testing facility

Figure 4. Pressures, strains and panel deformation time histories for slamming of the G-C70 panel at 3m/s and 10°

Fig. 7 Effect of impact velocity on strains at centre and chine edge of panels

Fig. 5 Schematic of the panel showing positions of pressure measurement points, a =60, b = 107.5, c = 120 and d = 200 mm

Fig. 8 Effect of impact velocity on bending moments at the centre and chine edge of panels normalised to uniform pressure based predictions

Fig. 6 Pressure comparison between rigid and deformable sandwich panels for water slamming impact at 3 m/s

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